

Challenges in the Development of Social Science Curriculum

Abstract

The social science is one of the core subject in teaching secondary school levels and it demands the area experts to deliver the historical views and also based on the curriculum the experts going to be trained with different types of learning experience in the development of social interest with instructional materials to give a lot of experience with different types of co-curricular activities and curricular activities . It also encashes and demands the values related skills to train in a proper way towards a social science curriculum.

Keywords: Curriculum, Conflicting, Acquisitions, Concurrent, Challenge, Lack, Crucial, Instructional

Introduction

The social science as a core subject to be taught in secondary schools, demand that specialist teachers be trained and provided with Suitable Resource materials including text books so that they can deliver. Their lessons are effectively, the absence of related instructional materials in secondary schools. Lack of trained teachers and other similar problems serves as barriers to the achievement of numerous objectives in social science view of this situation, the teaching and learning of social science tends to be in effective in this school. Non specialist teachers are employed to teach social science and they apply the methods of teaching traditional subjects like history, geography, economics, and civics. The quality of social science teachers and effectiveness of their instructional strategies in the class room are crucial in the effective implementation of the programmed. Social science teachings are yet to involve learners adequately in active learning engagement condemned the expository method which is responsible for the poor implementation of the social science curriculum and consequent, Poor appreciation by learners of knowledge, values, attitudes and the skills in social science curriculum.

Aim of the Study

1. To develop the aesthetic value in studying of social science.
2. To develop the cultural heritage related to history.
3. To enhance the critising habits in social science.
4. To empower the moral and ethical values of social studies.
5. To know the rich culture and civilizations in history.
6. To emphasize for a wide range of views towards society.
7. To inculcate the spirit of enquiry and to eradicate the superstitions.
8. To develop the sense of attitude , appreciation, interest, skill and tempo in social science.
9. For the encashment of societal knowledge through wide reading.
10. To know the perceptual views of social science and science.

Social science is not the study of history, geography and civics. As a separate discipline social science asks question, raise issues, face problems, present needs and identifies realities. The concept of social science has been drawn from the disciplines of social science and humanities namely; sociology, Anthropology, ethics, History, geography, and Religion.

Negative Past Experiences with Social Science

The finding that an unacceptably of pre service or in service secondary school teachers shared a negative perception of their past encounters with social science present serious challenge. The cumulative percentage of participants who described their past social studies courses as being either very interesting or interesting was 58 percent. The fact most secondary education programs either offer only one course that concentrates on social science methods or combine it with other content areas raises the question of whether it is expecting too much from professors to have them strive to alter the negative perception that many

Yogeesh A

Lecturer,
Deptt.of Education,
Digvijaya Rural College of
Education, Tumkur
Karnataka

Harish R

Asst. Professor,
Deptt.of Education,
KSEF College of Education
Northern Extension,
Tumkur, Karnataka

secondary teachers have of social science. After all, how much enthusiasm for teaching social science can professors really be expected to generate, over the course of a semester, among those who have found social science to be anything but interesting?

A related issue is the temptation for individuals to equate the uninteresting with the unimportant many secondary school teachers are likely to have experienced disengagement on a cognitive and effective level with the content of social science courses.

The first challenge is how to change the negative perception that many in-service secondary school teacher have of social science and how to convince them that it is an important subject in the curriculum.

Lack of Interest in Teaching Social Science

What should come as surprise is the connection between the negative past experience of the teachers and their current Lack of interest in teaching social science. Twice as many of them reported their interest level for teaching social science before enrolling in the course as being low compared to the other subject, actually the finding that a majority of these participants reported their interest level as being medium. One would like to think that the low interest level that many pre service or in service secondary teachers may have for teaching social science before taking a social science methods course is not necessarily indicative of what their interest level will be when they are about to complete one. Unfortunately, such optimism appears ill-founded. When competing against the other content area in the traditional secondary school curriculum for the participant's selection as their most preferred content area, social science fares well.

The second challenge awaiting teachers is changing the reality that many secondary school teachers have concluded that other subjects in the curriculum are more desirable to teach than social science. Unless their minds are changed, the secondary status of social science in the curriculum will continue.

Confusion Over the Nature of Social Science.

Although the history of social science is replete with conflicting views about its nature and definition. Secondary teachers should fundamentally understand that field of study that draws content from a variety of sources. The participant had to consider whether or not it was difficult to define social science. Of the participants who were completing the course, 58 percent did not think it was, and 9.6 percent were undecided. The participants had to determine if the term social science really means a combination of history and geography. Of the participants who were complete the course, 32.5 percent agreed with the statement, 52.5 percent disagreed with the statement, and 15 percent were undecided. The result of were disappointing because just over half the participants social science to be something other than a combination of history and geography.

Conflicting/Conservative Sociological Beliefs.

One of the major goals for social science should be to help develop citizens who have the commitment and the skills needed to help close the gap between the democratic ideals of our nation and

societal realities. That goal, stated in various forms, has long been advocated by social science educators. Although the participants had progressive sociological beliefs generally, their responses on specific items reflected positions. That finding seems to relate directly to important issues in multicultural education, one of which is the difference that is likely to exist between the life experiences and sociological perspectives of teachers and their students who are members of diverse cultural groups. Because most teachers come, and will continue to come, from a middle-class background, the sociological perspective they bring to the classroom may be far more conservative and benign than that of minority parents and children. That difference in perspective is inherent in both items that were specific in nature. The fourth challenge is to encourage pre-service and in-service secondary teachers to adopt and teach the all-important social science goal of working to improve society. A conflict may exist between their general agreement with the ideals of that broad goal and their conservative sociological beliefs on specific issues.

Selecting What to Teach

The number of topics deemed pertinent to social science education at the pre-service level continues to expand .As the content demands increase. So does the pressure on professors to prepare pre-service secondary teachers adequately for an increasing number of responsibilities. The sheer number of topics can leave teachers perplexed about finding enough time to cover some much less all, of them. Some of these topics crucial issues and include the following under the description of what to teach in social science creating a civic culture, the hidden curriculum, student motivation, thinking skills, values education, global education, multicultural studies, gender studies, educational technology, alternative assessment, meeting the needs of students with disabilities, and academic freedom. One of the greatest challenges facing teachers is how to use the limited amount of time available to them in a prudent manner. Among the possible explanations for the lack of practical significance, one that deserves careful consideration suggests that the ideals of social science education.

The fifth challenge is selecting is and teaching content that is new, challenging, complex, and specific, rather than that which is redundant, simple, and general.

Using a Concurrent Social Science Field Experience

All the instructional strategies that are recommended in elementary social science methods (ex; cooperative learning, role-playing, simulation, inquiry, group and independent project) encourage socially interactive and active learning experiences, one would naturally think that field experience placements would be made with directing teachers who model these strategies.

Instructors must place each secondary school teachers who can provide encouragement, positive modeling, and support for teaching social science. Simply finding directing teachers who are willing, to have in-service secondary teachers in their classrooms is not an acceptable nor a successful strategy for making field experience placements.

Lack of Instructional Materials

In-adequate supply and utilization of instructional materials including textbooks which can increase teachers/students awareness and reinforce learning is obstacles to the teaching of social science in secondary schools. There is general shortage of books in some schools subjects. If the new social books is not more than revival of subjects like History, geography, Economics and sociology than there dearth of appropriate textbooks for social science. Social science a subject is closely related to humanities and the social-studies. Therefore a single text book may not have sufficient material represent this broad integrated social science.

Inappropriate Method of Teaching and Learning Social Science

Through social science can develop a positive attitude towards good citizenship. The realization of the numerous objectives of social science will be achieved if teachers apply social science method, expository- method, excursion method and Assignment method in their teaching and learning social science. Objectives of social science should be to help students to develop the ability to make reflective decisions in order to resolve individual and social problems a will as participating intelligently in social actions. Social science emphasis an interdisciplinary approach to the study of man interacting and coping with problems in society. Appropriate method to facilitate such interaction and cooperation among the learners and teachers should be encouraged.

Problem of Evolution and Assessment

In appropriate structuring of curriculum for instruction and teaching constitute another hindrance to the teaching of social science? Social science is an open ended subject it may be difficult to standardized answer and achievements. It is expected that social science should have positive effects on human behavior even though human behavior is to easy to evaluate it has been generally agreed that performance in social science either in or outside the class room can be evaluated. Experts are working hard to introduce evaluation criteria for measuring attitudinal performance.

Resource Centers Problem

Lack of provision for and lack resource centers secondary school also constitute a problem to the teaching and learning of social science the development of resource centers in schools and colleges is closely connected with the social science trend away from the traditional class instruction towards individual learning. Group learning, independent learning inquiry and discovery method.

Lack of Seminars Workshop and Conferences for Social Science Teachers.

Organized seminars, workshops and conferences provide opportunities for interaction learning and teaching. It also caters for appropriate reception of information and instruction on issues and problems. Mention must be also, only in passing, of the skepticism of pupils, parents and headmasters as to the relative merit of school studies in the social curriculum.

Lack of organized seminars, workshops and conferences contribute to the lukewarm attitude of

social science teachers in secondary schools. The teachers themselves have stressed adequately the role and prospect for studying social science.

Weekly Course Hours and Lack of Physical Conditions

Participants agree that in order process of education to be effective and productive they should be allocated enough time and necessary physical conditions, and because they lack elements in question having problems afterwards is indispensable. Seen as problem for other branches excess of students in classroom is assessed within lack of physical conditions. And also not having a laboratory or classroom belonging social science at schools generally is seen as not giving enough importance to the social science.

Lack of Interdisciplinary Approach in the Acquisitions

It is determined that the teachers generally think that the whole of social science disciplines are reflected to the acquisitions in social science program. Together with that the teachers' argue that in the social science program prepared with the interdisciplinary emotionality acquisitions in more discipline should be given more places.

Teaching Concept, Value and Skills

As it is well known social science program is based on information, skills and value perceptions. In this sense, it is important the concept, skills and values, which are headstones of social sciences; program should be understood and acquired. When teacher's views are analyzed, it is understood that all of the participants think concepts, values and skills included in social science programs are not able to be acquired by the students. In this sense, teachers claim and criticized they had not been provided with a guiding activity or method on teaching concept skills value, had not been given an education on teaching concept skills value and being given more importance on functions of social science so causing elements mentioned to remain in the background.

Suggestions

1. This work is subject to suggestions for possible solution to the problems associated with the teaching and learning of social science in secondary schools.
2. The suggestion will contribute a great deal to the increasing needs of the government, teacher and students of social science.
3. In line with this, the following suggestion is made to be adopted by the government and their educational agencies, seminar and conferences organized as well as teachers and students of social science in secondary schools.
4. Teachers who are trained in social science thought to be employed to teach the subject secondary schools. If non specialist is allowed to handle social science, students will not benefit in the subject.
5. Social science teachers should develop effective methods of teaching and learning so as to make way for easy realization of its rich objective.
6. Adequate funds should be made available to secondary schools by the government to enable them establish resource centers in various schools.

7. Resource persons should be invited to schools to help the teachers in teaching technique and on the correct use of the instructional material, as this will in turn help the teachers and learning of the subject more meaningful and interesting.
8. The government should equip all secondary school libraries with sufficient and relevant textbooks in social science.
9. Social science should be introduced in senior secondary schools like the traditional subject to serve as a motivating factor to those in secondary schools.
10. Finally the researcher wishes to suggest that the central and state government along with their educational agencies should support the teaching and learning of social science for all secondary schools.
11. There should be a laboratories/ classrooms special for social science in secondary schools.
12. Allowance should be separated for the study trips within the scope of social science.
13. The objectives which was prepared inter disciplinary approach should be given more space in social science curriculum.
14. Social science license programs should be revised and there should be lessons on teaching concepts, values and abilities.

Conclusion

A social science teacher must see himself as a facilitator of learning and should therefore exhibit desirable behavior to harmonize the nature and effectiveness of teaching and learning social science. Appropriate methods should be use at all times to make the lesson interesting and rewarding. The teacher should maintain a free questioning atmosphere in the class room for his students to

develop positive attitudes to learn. Finally, it must be emphasized that the role of a teacher in the teaching and learning social science is quite a challenging one. It follows that the teacher must be fully prepared to be able expose the students to the atmosphere of learning and appreciation of day to day social problems and solution in his interest and for the well being of the society.

References

1. Esu, A.E.O., & Inyang-Abia, M.E.(2004). Social studies; Technogies, methods and media. Port Harcourt; Double Diamond Publications.
2. Akpabio a.j (1984) Social studies for junior secondary school and colleges PAICO Ltd. 9Press and Books) Calabar.
3. George, A.,M,and Madan,A. 92009). Teaching social science in schools. New DEHLHI: Sage Publicatuons Pvt. Ltd.
4. Misra, Salil and Rajan, Asish (2012). Teaching of social science: History, Context and challenges in Vandana SAXEa (ed.), Nuturing the Expert within, New Dehlu: peeerson.
5. Kongawada N.B (2016). Understanding Discipline and Pedagogy: Social science, Gadag; vidyanidhi Prakahana
6. Binning A.C. and Binning D.H. (1952). Teaching of social studies in Secondary, Bombay: Tata McGraw Hill publishing co. Ltd.....
7. Mkpa, M. A. (1987) Curriculum development and implementation. Owerri:Totan publishers Ltd.,
8. Batra, P. (Ed) (2010).Social science Learning in Schools: Perspective and Challenges. New Delhi: Sage Publication India Pvt. Ltd.
9. Arora,P (2014).Exploring the science of society. Journal of Indian Education., New Delhi:NCERT.